

Ultrasonic Studies for the Micro Estimation of Lead(II) with Diethyldithiocarbamate

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Ultrasonic velocity measurements to an accuracy of $\pm 0.05\%$ have been determined in the micro estimation of lead(II) using sodium diethyldithiocarbamate as reagent at 25° . The adiabatic compressibilities calculated yielded results of quantitative significance.

IN recent years sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC) has been used for gravimetric and volumetric estimations¹⁻³ of many metal ions. No ultrasonic studies involving the compound, however, has been reported in the literature.

The present investigation is therefore initiated to estimate lead(II) on microscale with NaDDC by ultrasonic velocity and adiabatic compressibility measurements.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analar grade. Triple distilled water was used throughout. The solution of NaDDC was prepared fresh. The solutions of metal ions and NaDDC of desired strengths were prepared from the concentrated stock solutions. Lead diethyldithiocarbamate in sufficiently dilute solution was not found to precipitate.

The investigations were made at 25° by circulating thermostated water around the measuring cell. Ultrasonic velocity was determined using a single crystal variable path interferometer, working at 1 MHz and capable of yielding a velocity measurement to an accuracy of $\pm 0.05\%$. The measuring cell containing 5 ml solution of metal salt was connected to the out-put terminal of the high frequency generator. The micrometer was slowly moved till the anode current on the meter on high frequency generator showed a maximum. A number of maxima readings of the anode were passed and their number, n was counted. The total distance, d moved by the micrometer gave the value of the wavelength, λ with the help of the following equation

$$d = n \lambda / 2$$

Once the λ is known the velocity, v in the liquid can be easily calculated with the help of the relation

$$v = \lambda F, \text{ where } F \text{ is the frequency.}$$

The procedure was repeated after the addition of 0.5 ml NaDDC each time. The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

10*[NaDDC] = 4.0 N; 10*[Lead nitrate] = 2.0 N	
Temp. = 25° ; Vol. of lead nitrate solution = 5.0 ml	
Observed end point	2.48 ml
Calculated end point	2.50 ml
Metal ions found	0.412 μ g
Metal ions calculated	0.414 μ g

A bicapillary pycnometer and an accurate analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.0001 gm were used for the determination of density and micro-burette was used for the addition of NaDDC solution. The adiabatic compressibility, β of the solution was calculated by Newton and Laplace equation⁴.

$$\beta = 1/ev^2$$

where v and e are the ultrasonic velocity and density of the solution, respectively.

Results and Discussion

In aqueous solutions of metal salt, the ultrasonic velocity generally increases with increasing concentration of the salt, whereas the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increase of concentration. Abnormal behaviour in solutions of lead nitrate of course has been reported⁵⁻⁷.

In the present investigation the ultrasonic velocity of metal salt solution was first found to decrease on addition of NaDDC and then increased, and β of the salt solution on addition of NaDDC was first found to increase and then decreased.

Fig. 1 depicts changes of ultrasonic velocity and β due to addition of NaDDC to metal ions. The

curves show negative and positive deviation from linearity in ultrasonic velocity and β , respectively.

Fig. 1.

The ultrasonic velocity is dependent on many factors like intra-molecular forces⁹, non ideality

Fig. 2.

in free length⁹ and interaction due to ion-association or chelation. The ion-association in the case of NaDDC and many metal ions are reported in the literature. The advantage of ion-association of lead(II) and NaDDC are taken for the micro estimation of metal ions by ultrasonic velocity and β measurements.

The values of excess compressibility¹⁰, β^E , with the addition of NaDDC are depicted in Fig. 2.

Since the excess of compressibility is a measure of the extent of deviation from ideal behaviour, it is also a measure of the extent of interaction due to ion-association or chelation between NaDDC and metallic ions. The maximum deviation is a stage which shows the completion of the derivative formation. The end point is well marked in Fig. 1 and 2. The results are summarised in Table 1.

The experimental observations were found to be in excellent agreement with the calculated results, and reproducible within $\pm 0.05\%$.

NaDDC forms water insoluble complex salt of the type

where M is the metal and n its valency. These compounds were found to be soluble in organic solvents, such as chloroform, ether and acetone.

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